

Systematic review: PRISMA checklist and flow diagram

Locating qualitative academic publications for reviewing tenants' and landlords' renting experiences and interaction in the Majority World

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Table 1 presents the checklist and **Figure 1** the flow diagram as recommended for reporting by [PRISMA 2020](#). Non-italicised text in Table 1 represents specifications and elements considered to be essential. Those written in italics are considered supplementary information that may enhance the completeness and usability of systematic review reports.

Table 1. PRISMA checklist

Section and Topic	Specifications	Elements recommended for reporting
TITLE		
	Identify the report as a systematic review	Identified
	Aim	Reviewing private tenants' and landlords' renting experiences and interaction
	Objective	Locating publication for reviewing
	Population	Private tenants and landlords
	Geography	Majority World
	<i>Designs of included studies</i>	<i>Qualitative academic publications</i>
ABSTRACT		
	PRISMA 2020 Abstracts	Per PRISMA 2020 Abstracts checklist
INTRODUCTION		
RATIONALE	Current state of knowledge and its uncertainties	While everyday experiences and interactions between private tenants and landlord in the Anglo-Saxon and older EU member states ("Minority World") are well-researched, little is known about the matter in the rest of the world ("Majority World"). Assembling this expectedly small and fragmented literature for synthesis holds significant academic and ethical importance for knowledge and knowledge representation.
	Why it is important to do the review?	The challenges faced by private tenants and landlords in the Majority World are likely more salient and fundamentally different from those elsewhere.
	Are other systematic reviews addressing the same (or a largely similar) questions available?	While the number of systematic reviews on the renting arrangements in the Minority World are increasing, only one scoping review on rental arrangements in the Majority World has been identified, and it dates back nearly 30 years.
OBJECTIVES	Objective(s) or question(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the geographical and temporal distribution of academic knowledge concerning the renting experiences and interactions between private tenants and landlords in the Majority World? 2. What are the collective affective experiences that drive the actions and interactions of private tenants and landlords in the Majority World?

METHODS			
ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA	Design(s)	Any qualitative study whose participants are either private tenants and/or private landlords	
	Setting(s)	Any country of the Majority World (excludes all developed countries)	
	Year of publication	Since 1990	
	Language	English	
	Publication status	Published academic articles, books and book chapters	
	Groups used in and focus of the synthesis	The renting experiences and interaction between private tenants and landlords	
	<i>Rationales for any notable restrictions to study eligibility</i>	<i>Only the under-research and under-represented countries of the Majority World are included, where tenants/landlords' challenges also more salient and different from those experienced in the developed countries</i>	
INFORMATION SOURCES	SCOPUS	10 January 2023, https://www.scopus.com/home.uri	
	WEB OF SCIENCE	10 January 2023, https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/webofscience-platform/	
	Housing Studies	17 January 2023, https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/chos20	
	International Journal of Housing Policy	17 January 2023, https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/reuj20	
	Geoforum	18 January 2023, https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/geoforum	
	Urban Studies	18 January 2023, https://journals.sagepub.com/home/usj	
	Habitat International	19 January 2023, https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/habitat-international	
	Google Scholar	20 January 2023, https://scholar.google.com/	
	Peer recommendations	January-March 2023, academic colleagues	
	Others	January-March 2023, references cited in study reports	
	SEARCH STRATEGY	PICO STYLE (validated through piloting but not peer reviewed)	Population (string 1)
Context (string 2)			(housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*) OR (Rooming AND hous*))
Study design (string 3)			(qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies")
OTHER INCLUSION CRITERIA		Geography	The Majority World: excludes the developed countries (AUS, AUT, BEL, CAN, CHE, DEU, DNK, ELA, ESP, FIN, FRA, GBR, GRC, IRL, ITA, ISL, JPN, LIE, LUX, MLT, NLD, NOR, NZL, PRT, SWE, USA)
		Timeline	1990-2022 (last partial review 1995)
	Language	English (sole access)	
	Reference	Articles, books, book chapters (proxy for quality)	
SCOPUS	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ((private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (hmo* AND resident*) OR (hmo* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*))) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies"))) AND (EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "United Kingdom") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "United States") OR EXCLUDE		

	(AFFILCOUNTRY, "Australia") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Canada") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Sweden") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Germany") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Netherlands") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Italy") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Japan") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "New Zealand") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Denmark") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Ireland") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Norway") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Spain") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Austria") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Belgium") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "France") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Switzerland") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Portugal") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Cyprus") OR EXCLUDE (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Finland")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "bk")) AND (EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1989) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1988) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1987) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1986) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1985) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1984) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1982) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 1976)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "EART") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "AGRI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "BIOC"))
WEB OF SCIENCE	(private AND (tenant* OR renter*)) OR lodger* OR squatter* OR flatmate* OR (HMO* AND resident*) OR (HMO* AND tenant*) OR (private AND landlord*) OR (tenant* AND landlord*) OR (landlord*-tenant* OR tenant*-landlord*) (Topic) AND (housing OR home OR house OR flat OR apartment OR flat-share OR (hous* AND "in multiple occupation") OR (rooming AND hous*) OR (boarding AND hous*)) (Topic) AND (qualitative OR interview OR ethnograph* OR "case study" OR "case studies") (Topic) and Infectious Diseases or Forestry or Water Resources or Genetics Heredity or Mathematical Computational Biology or Archaeology or Biochemistry Molecular Biology or Biotechnology Applied Microbiology or Chemistry or Critical Care Medicine or Emergency Medicine or Imaging Science Photographic Technology or Instruments Instrumentation or Mechanics or Medical Ethics or Neurosciences Neurology or Oceanography or Parasitology or Physics or Polymer Science or Food Science Technology or Meteorology Atmospheric Sciences or Pharmacology Pharmacy or Plant Sciences or Zoology or Agriculture or Geriatrics Gerontology or Veterinary Sciences or Surgery or Mathematics or Nutrition Dietetics or Geology or Immunology or Obstetrics Gynecology or Gastroenterology Hepatology (Exclude - Research Areas) and English (Languages) and ENGLAND or USA or UNITED KINGDOM or AUSTRALIA or CANADA or SCOTLAND or SWEDEN or NETHERLANDS or GERMANY or ITALY or NEW ZEALAND or NORWAY or DENMARK or FRANCE or NORTH IRELAND or SPAIN or BELGIUM or IRELAND or FINLAND or GREECE or UK or AUSTRIA or JAPAN or PORTUGAL or SWITZERLAND or WALES (Exclude - Countries/Regions)
Housing Studies	Manual title/abstract screening of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: "renting", which also returned "rented, rental or rent" (2.7% relevant hits of the total)
International Journal of Housing Policy	Manual title/abstract screening of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: "renting", which also returned "rented, rental or rent" (1.0% relevant hits of the total).
Geoforum	Manual title/abstract screening of the first most-relevant 400 publications; separate searches with the keywords: "renting" and "housing"; (0.8% relevant hits of the total)
Urban Studies	Manual title/abstract screening of the first most-relevant 300

		publications (searches for “renting”; 2.3% relevant hits of the total)
	Habitat International	Manual title/abstract screening of the first most-relevant 300 publications; keyword: “renting” (3.7% relevant hits of the total)
	Google Scholar	Manual title/abstract screening of the first 300 publications (searches for “renting”; 1.0% relevant hits of the total)
SELECTION PROCESS	How many reviewers screened each record?	1
	Screening approach	First title → If title unclear, the abstract is checked → If abstract not clear, the whole paper is checked
	Machine learning	Not applicable (the process was fully manual)
	Initial coding	Country of the case study

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram

